

ISTANBUL

CLIMATE-NEUTRAL BY 2030
EU MISSION CITY

The City of Istanbul, in Turkey, is situated in the Marmara Region and It has a transitional climate between the Black Sea and the Mediterranean and is one of the rainiest cities in the Marmara Region.

With 5.712 km² Istanbul has a population of 15,9 million, with expected growth for the next decades

LEADING ECONOMIC SECTORS IN ISTANBUL:

INDUSTRY

MANUFACTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS

TOURISM

MAIN SOURCES OF ENERGY GENERATED :

NATURAL GAS

RENEWABLES

MAIN SOURCES OF CO₂ EMISSIONS (2022):

BUILDING AND CONSTRUCTION

INDUSTRY

WASTE MANAGEMENT

TRANSPORT

MOBILITY PATTERNS:

AROUND 40% OF THE POPULATION COMMUTES BY FOOT,
28% USES PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION AND ONLY 15.9% TRAVEL BY CAR

SNAPSHOT OF ISTAMBUL ON CAPACITY BUILDING:

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

Governance and Policy

KEY AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

Finance

Implementation and technology

Social Innovation

TOPICS OF INTEREST:

Public-private-partnerships

PCED implementation

Business Models and financing schemes for energy-related projects

Funded by
the European Union

NATIONAL LEVEL:

FRAGMENTATION ACROSS LEVELS OF GOVERNMENTS ON CLIMATE POLICY

IN ISTANBUL:

CLIMATE INSTITUTIONAL ROLES ACROSS DEPARTMENTS

CROSS SECTORAL CLIMATE PLANS

COOPERATION WITH LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS

GOVERNANCE AND POLICY

Turkey ratified the Paris Agreement in 2021 and announced its net zero target for 2053. The country is updating its regulation and policy contexts towards its climate goals.

As key sectors for its decarbonisation strategies, Turkey focuses on the transport, industry, agriculture, waste, building and the energy sector with prioritization of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency for the built environment.

In terms of climate policy, the national government leads competencies in the climate change field, while regional and local authorities share competencies in the Environment and Environmental Health field.

In 2023, the city of Istanbul was selected as part of the EU 100 EU Mission Cities, to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.

Within the municipality of Istanbul, climate roles and responsibilities are shared across five departments - Environment, Urban Ecology & Biodiversity, Energy Management; Transport; IT & Smart City, and all departments are directly involved in the implementation of the city climate agenda. Given the vast territorial extension of the city and metropolitan area, an increased number of staff would be needed to improve the response to the city's needs.

The governance structure on climate is led by the Climate Change Directorate, under the Department of Environmental Protection and Development, facilitating the coordination among departments and following up with the Climate City Contracts process.

IMM Climate Change Directorate carries out action plans, projects and awareness raising activities for the city's climate policies.

Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan is prepared in 2021 for the climate neutrality target by 2050. In the plan, actions are determined and scenarios are modelled in order to reduce city's greenhouse gas emissions by 52.2 percent by 2030 compared to 2019 levels. In addition, Istanbul Sustainable Energy and Action Plan (SECAP) was prepared in the end of the 2023 to focus on energy actions and to identify new actions specifically for corporate energy emissions. Istanbul Green City Action Plan (GCAP) is currently in the preparation phase to be completed within next year. All these action plans reveal the Istanbul's efforts to become climate neutral. These experiences and steps will contribute to the preparations for the Climate City Contract, which adopts a very ambitious neutrality target as 2030.

The municipality actively involves local entities and stakeholders to promote climate awareness and action. Civic associations and universities are key actors engaged in co-designing sessions for the city climate plans and deployment of projects.

SOCIAL INNOVATION

The city of Istanbul engages with its local stakeholders and strives for an inclusive transition.

To this aim, the municipality focuses on raising awareness of climate change starting with the education sectors, including school campaigns, and with assemblies and mailing lists to address citizens' concerns and needs.

The municipality also strives to engage with its citizens and emphasize the importance of individual behavior for a positive contribution to climate neutrality.

Despite the engagement efforts, citizen and stakeholder participation is generally low. The main barriers identified to participation are lack of awareness/interest, lack of adequate communication channels, and fear from communities of changing behaviors.

To improve its social engagement capacity, Istanbul is looking to innovate in the following areas:

EDUCATION AND CULTURE

POLICY INNOVATION

PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATION WITH INTERMEDIARY LOCAL ORGANISATIONS

MUNICIPAL INTERNAL KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS

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IMPLEMENTATION AND TECHNOLOGY

Istanbul focuses on decarbonizing the Built environment, Transport, and Waste sectors.

When trying to reduce carbon emissions, Istanbul faces challenges related to limited accessible technological solutions, high upfront investments, and fragmented responsibility at different levels of government, leading to the need for more targeted regulations and enabling policies.

To enable emission reduction, the city focuses on digitalisation strategies and has a target on renewable energy production.

IMM has an inclusive remote control system for parks and gardens lighting, renewable energy control systems, energy counters, etc..

Also, 4% of the electricity consumption of IMM is furnished by solar energy, at the end of 2024, the part of solar energy will be 8%.

Istanbul has experience with PCEDs only at the designing stage, and it identifies engagement with the building and construction industry, homeowners/tenants, and the regional government as key to achieving a successful implementation.

CLIMATE AND ENERGY DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS

ADAPTATION SECTORS

LOCAL ENERGY RENEWABLE PRODUCTION

COLLABORATION

NEUTRALPATH key target sectors for the PCEDs implementation are: Built Environment, Energy and Mobility

FINANCING AND BUSINESS MODELS FOR PCEDS AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

The city of Istanbul is experienced in the use of public funding, especially concerning public investments in public infrastructure, and Third-party financing. EU-funded projects contribute to funding specific areas such as renewable energy, circular economy, and other related to sustainable development.

Overall, the city is interested in enhancing its financing capability using financial schemes, mixing different investment tools, attracting private capital and structuring investment planning for energy efficiency-related projects.

A significant priority includes designing effective business models specifically tailored for the PCED.

As part of its Climate City Contract under the EU Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, Istanbul is developing an Investment Plan as a comprehensive long-term economic and financial strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

Public funding
Third-party financing
Climate Neutrality Investment Plan

INTERESTED IN LEARNING ABOUT:

Business models for energy-related projects
Blended Finance
Mobilise private investments

The Capacity Building Program will support the upskilling of public authorities and local communities across these key cross-cutting areas and the Key Target Sectors to enable successful PCED implementation and unlock the systemic transformation necessary to achieve climate neutrality.

If you want to know more:

Istanbul's new Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan

Istanbul's Climate Change Action Plan

Turkey's International Energy Strategy

Citizens Aid Platform

neutralpath.eu/

2030
NEUTRALPATH

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